

RDFS Turtle Daftar Episode The Flash

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Konversi table bersisi data episode The Flash menjadi RDF turtle

1. Dataset

Data ditemukan di: [https://en.wikipedia.org/wiki/List_of_The_Flash_episodes#Season_1_\(2014-15\)](https://en.wikipedia.org/wiki/List_of_The_Flash_episodes#Season_1_(2014-15)) berisi tentang daftar episode pada serial TV The Flash yang tayang di The CW Television Network. Gambar 1 menunjukkan daftar episode pada serial The Flash. Namun, pada artikel ini data yang digunakan hanya tiga baris teratas yaitu episode 1-3.

Season 1 (2014–15) [edit]
Main article: The Flash (season 1)

No. overall	No. in season	Title	Directed by	Written by	Original air date	Prod. code	U.S. viewers (millions)
1	1	"Pilot"	David Nutter	Story by: Greg Berlanti & Andrew Kreisberg & Geoff Johns Teleplay by: Andrew Kreisberg & Geoff Johns	October 7, 2014	296648	4.83 ^[8]
2	2	"Fastest Man Alive"	David Nutter	Story by: Greg Berlanti & Andrew Kreisberg Teleplay by: Andrew Kreisberg & Geoff Johns	October 14, 2014	3J5352	4.27 ^[9]
3	3	"Things You Can't Outrun"	Jesse Warn	Alison Schapker & Grainne Godfree	October 21, 2014	3J5353	3.59 ^[10]
4	4	"Going Rogue"	Glen Winter	Geoff Johns & Kai Yu Wu	October 28, 2014	3J5354	3.53 ^[11]
5	5	"Plastique"	Dermott Downs	Aaron Helbing & Todd Helbing & Brooke Eikmeier	November 11, 2014	3J5355	3.46 ^[12]
6	6	"The Flash Is Born"	Millicent Shelton	Jaime Paglia & Chris Rafferty	November 18, 2014	3J5356	3.73 ^[13]
7	7	"Power Outage"	Larry Shaw	Alison Schapker & Grainne Godfree	November 25, 2014	3J5357	3.47 ^[14]
8	8	"Flash vs. Arrow"	Glen Winter	Story by: Greg Berlanti & Andrew Kreisberg Teleplay by: Ben Sokolowski & Brooke Eikmeier	December 2, 2014	3J5358	4.34 ^[15]
9	9	"The Man in the Yellow Suit"	Ralph Hemecker	Todd Helbing & Aaron Helbing	December 9, 2014	3J5359	4.66 ^[16]
10	10	"Revenge of the Rogues"	Nick Copus	Kai Yu Wu & Geoff Johns	January 20, 2015	3J5360	3.87 ^[17]
11	11	"The Sound and the Fury"	John F. Showalter	Alison Schapker & Brooke Eikmeier	January 27, 2015	3J5361	4.08 ^[18]
12	12	"Crazy for You"	Rob Hardy	Aaron Helbing & Todd Helbing	February 3, 2015	3J5362	3.60 ^[19]
13	13	"The Nuclear Man"	Glen Winter	Andrew Kreisberg & Katherine Walczak	February 10, 2015	3J5363	3.66 ^[20]
14	14	"Fallout"	Steve Surjik	Keto Shimizu & Ben Sokolowski	February 17, 2015	3J5364	4.01 ^[21]
15	15	"Out of Time"	Thor Freudenthal	Todd Helbing & Aaron Helbing	March 17, 2015	3J5365	3.69 ^[22]
16	16	"Rogue Time"	John Behring	Story by: Grainne Godfree Teleplay by: Brooke Eikmeier & Kai Yu Wu	March 24, 2015	3J5366	3.33 ^[23]
17	17	"Tricksters"	Ralph Hemecker	Andrew Kreisberg	March 31, 2015	3J5367	3.67 ^[24]
18	18	"All Star Team Up"	Kevin Tancharoen	Grainne Godfree & Kai Yu Wu	April 14, 2015	3J5368	3.67 ^[25]

Gambar 1. Daftar episode The Flash

2. Format Turtle

```
@prefix xsd: <http://www.w3.org/2001/XMLSchema#> .
@prefix rdf: <http://www.w3.org/1999/02/22-rdf-syntax-ns#> .
@prefix rdfs: <http://www.w3.org/2000/01/rdf-schema#> .
@prefix schema: <https://schema.org/> .

@prefix x: <http://example.com/> .

x:episode a rdfs:class ;
```

```
rdfs:subClassOf schema:TVEpisode .

x:productionCode a rdf:Property ;
  rdfs:domain x:episode ;
  rdfs:range xsd:string .

x:writtenBy a rdf:Property ;
  rdfs:domain x:episode ;
  rdfs:range schema:person .

x:USWiewersInMillions a rdf:Property ;
  rdfs:domain x:episode ;
  rdfs:range xsd:float .

x:storyBy a rdf:Property ;
  rdfs:subPropertyOf x:writtenBy;
  rdfs:domain x:episode ;
  rdfs:range schema:person .

x:teleplayBy a rdf:Property ;
  rdfs:subPropertyOf x:writtenBy;
  rdfs:domain x:episode ;
  rdfs:range schema:person .

<x:DavidNutter> a schema:Person ;
  schema:name "David Nutter"@en .

<x:GregBerlanti> a schema:Person ;
  schema:name "Greg Berlanti"@en .

<x:AndrewKreisberg> a schema:Person ;
  schema:name "Andrew Kreisberg"@en .

<x:GeoffJohns> a schema:Person ;
  schema:name "Geoff Johns"@en .

<x:JesseWarn> a schema:Person ;
  schema:name "Jesse Warn"@en .

<x:AlisonSchapker> a schema:Person ;
  schema:name "Alison Schapker"@en .

<x:GrainneGodfree> a schema:Person ;
  schema:name "Grainne Godfree"@en .

<x:296648> a x:episode ;
  x:productionCode "296648" ;
  schema:name "Pilot"@en ;
  schema:director x:DavidNutter ;
  x:storyBy x:GregBerlanti, x:AndrewKreisberg, x:GeoffJohns ;
  x:teleplayBy x:AndrewKreisberg, x:GeoffJohns ;
  x:datePublished: "2014-10-07"^^schema:date;
```

x:UsWiewersInMillions: "4.83"^^xsd:float .

```
<x:3J5352> a x:episode ;
  x:productionCode: "3J5352" ;
  schema:name "Fastest Man Alive"@en ;
  schema:director x:DavidNutter ;
  x:storyBy x:GregBerlanti, x:AndrewKreisberg, x:GeoffJohns ;
  x:teleplayBy x:AndrewKreisberg, x:GeoffJohns ;
  schema:datePublished: "2014-10-14"^^schema:date ;
  x:UsWiewersInMillions: "4.27"^^xsd:float .
```

```
<x:3J5353> a x:episode ;
  x:productionCode: "3J5353" ;
  schema:name "Things You Can't Outrun"@en ;
  schema:director x:DavidNutter ;
  x:writtenBy x:AlisonSchapker, x:GrainneGodfree ;
  schema:datePublished: "2014-10-21"^^schema:date ;
  x:UsWiewersInMillions: "3.59"^^xsd:float .
```

3. Gambar Visualisasi RDF

